

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the organization of independent learning in the process of higher education, the effective use of mobile technologies, and methods for solving students' problems related to virtual platforms.

Opportunities are being created to introduce modern information technology tools into the educational and training process of higher educational institutions of our country, as well as to improve pedagogical mechanisms for developing students' knowledge, skills, and abilities related to digital and mobile technologies, and to introduce innovative forms and methods of training pedagogical personnel by developing modern approaches. The didactic structure of developing digital competence in independent education of students includes determining learning goals in stages, selecting appropriate digital tools, delivering course content, practice and feedback, and assessments. Independent education does not mean learning by itself, but is an educational process aimed at improving students' digital skills. The ability to learn independently is the ability to set goals and independently solve complex problems. In addition, in developing students' scientific abilities, their satisfaction with the educational process is important. The MIT App Inventor platform also greatly helps students in independent learning. To work in the MIT App Inventor program, you must have an Internet connection and a Google account. To start working in this environment, you need to go to this link 61selects English for the environment interface. How can I install Russian in the App Inventor environment: Thus, digital literacy is based on the principle of enhancing the teaching-learning experience using digital resources so that students can discover the potential of learning in the digital age. Another way to develop independent work is to assign students projects that require the use of digital tools and resources. For example, you can ask students to create a multimedia presentation using PowerPoint or Prezi or create a digital portfolio using Google Sites. The types of digital resources and tools that students can use include: Online research databases: (These are digital libraries that provide access to a wide range of academic materials, such as journals, articles, and books); Educational applications: (These are software applications designed to provide students with educational content and activities); Digital textbooks: (These are electronic versions of traditional textbooks that can be accessed via a computer or mobile device); MIT App Inventor is a cloud-based visual development environment for Android applications. 1. "Designer" - at this stage, the interface

of the mobile application is designed. 2. "Blocks" - this stage is responsible for programming the mobile application. In the "Designer" mode, the interface of the mobile application is designed by placing various components (elements) installed in the development environment. The "Designer" mode includes 5 main blocks: 1. Palette - contains all components; 2. View - a window that simulates the mobile application screen (only one selected screen is displayed in the window, but we can create any number of screens in applications; 3. Components - this block displays components that have already been added to the application being developed; 4. Properties (component) - this block displays the properties of the selected component; 5. Media - acts as a cloud storage for photos, audio and video files. Let's return to the "Palette" block.

All components are divided into the following groups:

1. User interface - components of this group allow the user of the application to interact with it;
2. Layout - elements of this block are responsible for the location of components on the screen: horizontal, vertical or tabular;
3. Media - responsible for adding various media tools, such as video players, speech recognizers, voice recorders, etc.;
4. Drawing and animation - components for creating animations;
5. Sensors - allow the mobile application to obtain information by communicating with the sensors and sensors of the mobile device on which it is running;

Reforms in the field of education are having a positive effect on the prosperity and development of society. Increasing the intellectual potential of developed countries is an important factor in preparing mature, competitive personnel who can meet the requirements set by state educational standards and qualification requirements. It is inevitable to rationally use the scope of a person's psychological and pedagogical capabilities, to determine certain social prospects on this basis, and to realize, develop and mature each individual as a part of society and the people. In the process of education and upbringing, each teacher must create conditions for students to think independently, otherwise the student's mind will become so accustomed to ready-made templates and stereotypes that they will eventually follow any wrong or alien ideas. That is, opening up a wide range of non-traditional methods of organizing lessons, organizing interactive communication of students in lessons, helping their brains work better, become interested and think independently. In leading scientific educational institutions of the world, a number of scientific researches are being conducted on a number of problems, such as teaching students to learn independently based on innovative approaches, the need to organize, manage and control independent learning, gaps in the existing mechanisms of independent learning, inconsistencies in the system. This, in turn, requires a more in-depth study of existing approaches to the characteristics of students' independent learning activities, its essence, principles of organization, content and methods.

In conclusion, one of the specific tasks facing the higher education system today is to ensure the social activity of young people and the competitiveness of their knowledge, and to bring their theoretical and practical knowledge to the level of excellence. The didactic structure of developing digital competence in students' independent learning is based on the stages of determining learning objectives, selecting appropriate digital tools, delivering course content, practice and feedback, and evaluation. Independent learning does not mean learning by itself, but rather an educational process aimed at improving students' digital skills. Independent learning skills are the ability to set goals and solve complex problems independently. Also, in developing students' scientific abilities, their satisfaction with the learning process is important. Considering the above advantages, it follows that the organization of independent learning in the higher education system is of great importance.

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